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Agriculture waste pyrolysis and thermocomposting for renewable energy in sustainable agri-food sector

D3.1 GIS maps for the identification of soil for biomass

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

AGB	Above Ground Biomass
AGBD	Above-Ground Biomass Density
AVEPA	Agenzia Veneta per i Pagamenti
CERTH	Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
GA	Grant agreement
GEDI	Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
HI	Harvest Index
IoTs	Internet of Things
ISTAT	Istituto Nazionale di Statistica
JRC	Joint Research Centre
OSM	OpenStreetMap
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
TDP	TEAPOTS Digital Platform
TIS	TEAPOTS Integrated Solution
UNIPD-TESAF	Department of Land, Environment, Agriculture and Forestry of University of Padova
UTE	Uptoearth GmbH

Executive summary

This report describes the methodology applied for the delivery of GIS (Geographic Information Systems) maps created to identify suitable soil areas for biomass production in pilot areas, contributing to optimized feedstock selection and waste biomass utilization. This methodology will result, during the whole project lifetime, in the publication of the following maps:

- Four annual maps of cover crop classification
- Four annual maps of biomass
- Four annual maps providing estimation of available residues from agricultural crops and providing estimation of the potential exploitation of energy for biomass residues, considering also logistical and environmental aspects.

All maps are based on the mapping activities conducted in WP2 and follow the acquisition and analysis of multispectral and SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) data from different open-source satellites (T3.1). These maps will be issued with a resolution of 10m and will be available on the [project website](#)¹.

The 2024 annual maps are referred to the two physical pilots participating to the TEAPOTS projects (Filia Ghi in Greece and Ecofarm in Italy). Annual maps related to the virtual pilots will be issued by M18 to be available for T5.1 Prediction system of biomass yields and logistics.

The map images in this document are provided solely for illustrative purposes to aid in understanding the methodology and comparing maps created by TEAPOTS and JRC. For detailed map exploration and analysis, it is warmly recommended to use the demonstration tool available on the [project website](#).

¹ <https://www.teapots-project.eu/pilots>

Planned activities

The aim of Task 3.1 is to acquire multispectral and SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) data from different open-source satellites. Uptoearth GmbH (UTE) is the leader of T3.1 with the support of the Department of Land, Environment, Agriculture and Forestry of University of Padova (UNIPD-TESAF).

The task has started in January 2024 and will last 12 months. It consists of the following activities:

- Automatic satellite recognition of cultivated areas and respective crops: an algorithm based on convolutional neural networks will be developed to correctly classify cultivated geometries and crops, based on time series of multispectral data acquired by the Sentinel-2 satellite. The result will be four annual crop classification maps, supplemented with auxiliary data.
- Definition and classification of agricultural land: accurate field boundary information is of considerable importance for biomass estimation. Information obtained from field boundaries can provide valuable input for agricultural applications such as crop monitoring and yield forecasting.
- Mechanisation and energy valorisation of biomass: identification and definition of appropriate models for estimating available resources and development of an econometric model, based on a GIS (Geographic Information Systems) platform and satellite data, capable of estimating the available resources both ecologically and economically. The model will estimate the availability of biomass, the amount of biomass that can be removed and any geographic and orographic locations useful for logistical optimisation.
- Ground truth validation of satellite data classification models: TESA department of the UNIPD group, will collect field data to verify models developed by UTE in terms of: crop type recognition and biomass and canopy estimation, using results from T2.1 and pilots' real data.

1. Study areas

The developed GIS maps refer to the two physical pilots included in the projects, where the TIS (TEAPOTS Integrated Solution) is going to be applied and data are going to be gathered to develop the TDP (TEAPOTS Digital Platform).

In addition, four virtual replications (Veneto Region, France, The Netherlands, Germany) will be established near the end of the project, when models from the physical pilots will be refined to evaluate the benefits of TEAPOTS' results in different environments, different feedstocks and different dimension of end-users. Therefore, GIS maps will be also developed for the four virtual pilots.

As far as the two physical pilots, they have been identified respectively in Italy and Greece.

1.1 ECOFARM (Italy)

Ecofarm SRL OP is in Butera, a small municipality located in the province of Caltanissetta, in the southern part of Sicily Island, and involves several local agricultural entrepreneurs. The total farm area encompasses 1600 hectares to produce crops (wheat, and melon) and fruit trees (apricot, peach, grapes, olive trees, and almonds).

FIGURE 1: STUDY AREA LOCATION

The area considered for the study activity has a total extension of 3500 hectares and includes not only fruit trees and vineyards (arboreal or permanent crops), but also other herbaceous or temporary crops located in the surroundings of Ecofarm's property. This choice is functional to enhance the representativeness of physical pilots for virtual ones as explained in paragraph **6. Encountered issues and mitigation actions**.

This image displays the total area of interest for the Italian pilot, along with the specific crop type planted in each individual plot. The map of the pilot site is available for consultation on the [project website](#).

FIGURE 2. ITALIAN PILOT'S STUDY AREA AND CROP TYPE

The table below presents the details of plantation under examination:

TABLE 1. ITALIAN PILOT'S PLANTATIONS²

Plot Number	Plantation type/variety	Age	Plants number	Plantation extension (ha)
ECOFARM 0	Peach trees	1	2800	2.93
ECOFARM 1	Peach trees	3	5437	8.69
ECOFARM 2	Peach trees	5	2951	3.74
ECOFARM 3	Peach trees	5	2061	3.95
ECOFARM 4	Peach trees	5	1720	2.26
ECOFARM 5	Peach trees	5	871	1.12
ECOFARM 6	Peach trees	5	1310	1.51
ECOFARM 7	Peach trees	7	1404	1.74

² Missing values may refer to Not Applicable categorization or to Not Available information.

Plot Number	Plantation type/variety	Age	Plants number	Plantation extension (ha)
ECOFARM 8	Peach trees	0	850	1.56
ECOFARM 9	Peach trees	22	635	0.83
ECOFARM 10	Peach trees	1	435	0.76
ECOFARM 11	Vineyard	18	5480	1.62
ECOFARM 12	Vineyard	5	6560	1.13
ECOFARM 13	Temporary crops	0	-	4.24
ECOFARM 14	Vineyard/Table grape	13	3470	2.27
ECOFARM 15	Vineyard/ Nero D'Avola, Chardonnay, Petit Verdot	2	40000	9.25
ECOFARM 16	Temporary crops	0	-	1.12
ECOFARM 17	Vineyard/Table grape	12	3478	2.25
ECOFARM 18	Peach trees	17	1351	1.62
ECOFARM 19	Vineyard/Table grape	15	1664	1.38
ECOFARM 20	Vineyard/ Nero D'Avola	15	1792	1.49
ECOFARM 21	Vineyard/ Chardonnay, Petit Manseng	6	6880	1.90
ECOFARM 22	Fallow land	-	-	0.53
ECOFARM 23	Vineyard/ Nero D'Avola	12	2400	0.60
ECOFARM 24	Vineyard/Table grape	13	3951	1.90
ECOFARM 25	Vineyard/ Grillo	6	5440	1.30
ECOFARM 26	Vineyard/ Nero D'Avola	12	12000	3.13
ECOFARM 27	Vineyard/ Zibibbo, Catarratto, Chardonnay	7	30000	4.78
ECOFARM 28	Peach trees	21	3446	4.33
ECOFARM 29	Vineyard/ Nero D'Avola, Syrah	12	12000	4.11
ECOFARM 30	Peach trees	11	5549	6.52
ECOFARM 31	Apricot trees/ Mikado	7	329	0.55

Plot Number	Plantation type/variety	Age	Plants number	Plantation extension (ha)
ECOFARM 32	Vineyard/ Nero D'Avola	15	17000	3.79
ECOFARM 33	Vineyard/ Nero D'Avola	15	2000	0.88
ECOFARM 34	Nut trees	-	-	1.62
ECOFARM 35	Vineyard/ Nero D'Avola	15	1548	1.29
ECOFARM 36	Vineyard/ Inzolia	1	4800	1.29
ECOFARM 37	Vineyard/Table grape	14	6400	3.43
ECOFARM 38	Multi-year forest	-	-	0.69
ECOFARM 39	Vineyard/ Frappato	8	6560	1.84
ECOFARM 40	Peach trees	16	1175	2.72
ECOFARM 41	Apricot trees/ Lady cot	7	914	1.68
ECOFARM 42	Peach trees	11	5743	7.63
ECOFARM 43	Peach trees	14	4194	4.83
ECOFARM 44	Vine shoots/ Chardonnay	0	8000	1,92

1.2 FILIA GHI (Greece)

FILIA GHI is a winery located in Thessaly, Sofades, Greece. It is operating in a rural area with a lot of potential biomasses, spanning 13 hectares of vineyards, 0.4 hectares of olive trees, and 1 hectare of almond trees. The total area has been considered for the pilot.

FIGURE 2: STUDY AREA LOCATION

The area considered for the study activity has a total extension of 2000 hectares and includes not only fruit trees and vineyards (arboreal or permanent crops), but also other herbaceous or temporary crops located in the surroundings of Filia Ghi's property. This choice is functional to enhance the representativeness of physical pilots for virtual ones as explained in paragraph 6. ***Encountered issues and mitigation actions.***

This image displays the total area of interest for the Greek pilot, along with the specific crop type planted in each individual plot. The map of the pilot site is available for consultation on the [project website](#).

FIGURE 3. GREEK PILOT'S STUDY AREA AND CROP TYPE

The table below presents the details of plantation under examination:

TABLE 2. GREEK PILOT'S PLANTATIONS³

Plot Number	Plantation type/variety	Age	Plants	Plantation extension (ha)
FILIA GHI A1	Vineyard/ Malagouzia	4	4500	1.51
FILIA GHI A2	Vineyard/Moscato	20	2750	1.14
FILIA GHI A3	Vineyard/Limniona	4	1650	0.64
FILIA GHI A4	Vineyard/Syrah	16	1500	0.6

³ Missing values may refer to Not Applicable categorization or to Not Available information.

Plot Number	Plantation type/variety	Age	Plants	Plantation extension (ha)
FILIA GHI A5	Vineyard/Malbec	4	320	0.12
FILIA GHI A6	Vineyard/Malbec	4	650	0.26
FILIA GHI A7	Vineyard/Malagousia	14	500	0.19
FILIA GHI A8	Vineyard/Vermentino	4	2200	0.87
FILIA GHI A9	Vineyard/Merlot	14	1000	0.40
FILIA GHI A10	Vineyard/Malagousia	16	1920	0.76
FILIA GHI A11	Vineyard/Limniona	20	1500	0.60
FILIA GHI A12	Vineyard/Assyrtiko	18	1000	0.37
FILIA GHI A13	Vineyard/Moscato	14	625	0.24
FILIA GHI A14	Vineyard/Chardonnay	15	625	0.24
FILIA GHI A15	Vineyard/Assyrtiko	15	2000	0.81
FILIA GHI A16	Vineyard/Moscato	30	1500	0.63
FILIA GHI A17	Vineyard/Moscato, Syrah, Sultanine	-	1100	0.44
FILIA GHI A18	Vineyard/Sauvignon, Moscato	18	6500	2.74
FILIA GHI A19	Almond Trees	4	-	0.50
FILIA GHI A20	Almond Trees	4	-	0.20
FILIA GHI A21	Almond Trees	4	-	0.23
FILIA GHI A22	Almond Trees	4	-	0.06
FILIA GHI A23	Olive Trees/Arpecina	10	210	0.44

1.3 Pilot site characterization

To proceed with the satellite data acquisition and analysis, the first step has been to geolocate the two study areas. We have successfully georeferenced the areas and ensured the coordinates are precise for the satellite data analysis.

Firstly, accurate reference data, including high-resolution aerial images and GPS coordinates, have been acquired to serve as a basis for the georeferencing process. A geospatial database (geodatabase) has been then created to store all the relevant information and geometries of the crop areas. This database includes detailed geometries outlining the boundaries of each crop field.

Each crop area within the geodatabase has been classified based on several attributes:

- Crop type
- Planting distance or spacing between plants, to understand planting density and its impact on growth and yield.
- Phenological cycle, such as germination, flowering, and harvesting times, to track the growth stages over time.
- Cultivation practices, such as pruning, fertilization, irrigation, and other management activities, to understand the influence of these practices on crop development and health.

Through this comprehensive georeferencing and data classification process, we have established a robust foundation for analysing the satellite data, which will aid in monitoring crop health, predicting yields, and optimizing agricultural practices.

After that, some pieces of information have been retrieved from the pilots:

- Plantation varieties, extension, and spatial dispositions
- Identification of areas with grape coverage and its duration to determine regions that will not or will only partially be visible from satellites. This practice has been identified only at the Italian pilot site.
- Pruning periods, including amount of pruning, and specific areas for each plantation type.
- Data related to the harvesting periods and other significant events.

Both the geolocation of the pilot sites and the collection of the above-mentioned information required the direct involvement of the pilot partners. For the Italian pilot, three online meetings have been organized with the active participation of UNIPD-TESAF. For the Greek pilot, due to the accession of a new pilot partner into the Consortium, this activity has been mediated by CERTH.

2. Cover crop classification maps

Classification maps have been issued following a two-step approach: firstly, a land use classification has been performed and, after that, a binary classification has been applied to distinguish between perennial and non-perennial plantations. The full applied methodology is presented below.

2.1 Classification methodology

For land use classification, it has been necessary to initially mask areas to be excluded by the analysis. This included bare soils, water objects and urban areas. Subsequently, the pilots have been classified in five classes based on their vegetation coverage:

- Class 1 - Low vegetation coverage encompasses areas with minimal vegetation coverage, where vegetation is sparse or absent.
- Class 2 - Mid-low vegetation coverage comprises rotational crops such as cereals and other crops that do not require dense vegetation coverage.
- Class 3 – Middle vegetation coverage involves rotational crops that produce a significant foliage mass and leave a lot of residual biomass.
- Class 4 - Mid-high vegetation coverage comprehends perennial crops.
- Class 5 - High vegetation coverage contains forested and evergreen areas.

After the land use classification, a binary classification was applied to further categorize the areas into “permanent” and “temporary” plantations. The decision to adopt this terminology is to allow comparison between the crop classification performed for TEAPOTS project and the EUROCROPMAP 2022 developed by JRC and available [here](https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset/555e5d1d-1aae-4320-a716-2e6d18aa1e7c)⁴. According to the official definition, permanent crops are usually ligneous crops, such as trees or shrubs, which are not grown in rotation, but are harvested for several continuous years [1]. Temporary crops, instead, are sown and harvested during the same agricultural year, sometimes more than once per year [2]. This step helps in distinguishing crops and vegetation that are consistent year-round from those that change with seasons or crop rotations. The classification criteria have been established and validated with UNIPD-TESAF.

Based on this classification, the maps provide a detailed overview of the vegetation distribution and types within the study areas, allowing for better planning and analysis of agricultural practices, for monitoring crop health, and for optimizing resource allocation. Moreover, this step is crucial to fully understand the temporal and quantitative distribution of biomass, as well as the management of its residues in the field that can be allocated for biochar production.

The table below reports the adopted classification criteria:

⁴ <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset/555e5d1d-1aae-4320-a716-2e6d18aa1e7c>

TABLE 3. BINARY CLASSIFICATION OF PLANTATION TYPES IN PILOT AREAS

Plantation type	Binary classification
Almond Trees	Permanent
Olive Trees	Permanent
Peach Tree	Permanent
Vineyards	Permanent
Apple Tree	Permanent
Lemon Tree	Permanent
Woodland and Shrubland	Permanent
Common Wheat	Temporary
Durum Wheat	Temporary
Barley	Temporary
Rye	Temporary
Oats	Temporary
Maize	Temporary
Rice	Temporary
Triticale	Temporary
Potatoes	Temporary
Sugar Beet	Temporary
Sunflower	Temporary
Rapeseed and Turnip Rapeseed	Temporary
Soya	Temporary
Dry Pulses	Temporary
Grasslands	Temporary
Other rotary crops	Temporary

2.2 Comparison of classification results with EURO-CROP-2022

In 2022 the Joint Research Centre (JRC) has published an open-source map referred to 2022 covering European Union (EU-27 and Ukraine) which classifies the reference area based on crop type at 10m resolution [3].

JRC map adopts a binary classification to distinguish between permanent and temporary crops, urban areas and water bodies, woodland areas and crop type. Below we report the comparison between TEAPOTS classification maps for the physical pilots and JRC classification maps for the same areas.

FIGURE 4. COMPARISON BETWEEN JRC (UP) AND TEAPOTS (DOWN) CLASSIFICATION IN PERMANENT AND TEMPORARY CROPS IN THE ITALIAN PILOT. PLOTS ARE DELIMITED BY BLACK BORDERS

FIGURE 5. COMPARISON BETWEEN JRC (UP) AND TEAPOTS (DOWN) CLASSIFICATION IN PERMANENT AND TEMPORARY CROPS IN THE GREEK PILOT. PLOTS ARE DELIMITED BY BLACK BORDERS

In both pilots, the images (Figure 4 and Figure 5) highlight that the JRC map classifies better temporary crops compared to the TEAPOTS one, while the TEAPOTS map performs better in the classification of permanent crops.

FIGURE 6. COMPARISON BETWEEN JRC (UP) AND TEAPOTS (DOWN) CLASSIFICATION BETWEEN URBAN AREAS AND WATER BODIES IN THE ITALIAN PILOT. PLOTS ARE DELIMITED BY BLACK BORDERS. THE TEAPOTS MAP MASKS BOTH URBAN AREAS AND WATER BODIES SINCE THEY ARE NOT RELEVANT FOR THE PROJECT SCOPE. IN THIS CASE, URBAN AREAS IN BOTH MAPS ARE EXPOSED FOR COMPARISON

FIGURE 7. COMPARISON BETWEEN JRC (UP) AND TEAPOTS (DOWN) CLASSIFICATION BETWEEN URBAN AREAS AND BARE LANDS IN THE GREEK PILOT. PLOTS ARE DELIMITED BY BLACK BORDERS. THE TEAPOTS MAP MASKS BOTH URBAN AREAS AND BARE LANDS SINCE THEY ARE NOT RELEVANT FOR THE PROJECT SCOPE. IN THIS CASE, URBAN AREAS IN BOTH MAPS ARE EXPOSED FOR COMPARISON. WATER BODIES ARE NOT PRESENT IN THE GREEK PILOT

In both pilots, the images (Figure 6 and Figure 7) highlight that the TEAPOTS map performs better in the classification of urban/bare areas thanks to the application of OpenStreetMap (OSM) layer compared to JRC map that classifies some agricultural areas as urban/bare ones.

FIGURE 8. COMPARISON BETWEEN JRC (UP) AND TEAPOTS (DOWN) CLASSIFICATION FOR TEMPORARY CROPS IN THE ITALIAN PILOT. PLOTS ARE DELIMITED BY BLACK BORDERS

FIGURE 9. COMPARISON BETWEEN JRC (UP) AND TEAPOTS (DOWN) CLASSIFICATION FOR TEMPORARY CROPS IN THE GREEK PILOT. PLOTS ARE DELIMITED BY BLACK BORDERS.

In both pilots, the images (Figure 8 and Figure 9) highlight that JRC classification for temporary crops is more detailed than the TEAPOTS classification. This choice is in line with the project scope of focusing especially on temporary crops. However, despite a better performance of JRC in temporary crop classification, the comparison with TEAPOTS maps points out that the JRC classification presents some errors in distinguishing between bare soils or temporary crops and permanent crops especially in the Italian pilot.

FIGURE 10. COMPARISON BETWEEN JRC (UP) AND TEAPOTS (DOWN) CLASSIFICATION FOR PERMANENT CROPS IN THE ITALIAN PILOT. PLOTS ARE DELIMITED BY BLACK BORDERS

FIGURE 11. COMPARISON BETWEEN JRC (UP) AND TEAPOTS (DOWN) CLASSIFICATION FOR PERMANENT CROPS IN THE GREEK PILOT. PLOTS ARE DELIMITED BY BLACK BORDERS.

In both pilots, the images (Figure 10 and Figure 11) highlight that JRC classification for permanent crops is less detailed than the TEAPOTS classification. Conversely, considering the project scope, a more accurate classification is required and is presented in the TEAPOTS map. JRC maps, in fact, includes several permanent crops under a unique class named “Woodland and shrubland”. As a result, the TEAPOTS maps achieve a more accurate results for permanent crop classification.

We decided to develop an internal land use classification for our project instead of using the EURO-CROP-Map 2018 and EURO-CROP-Map 2022 classifications. This decision was driven by several reasons, which have been reported below.

First, considering the destination of the data that we are providing, it became clear that crop classification represents the fundamental basis of our entire project model. Any imperfections at this stage could lead to significant errors in data related to biomass, residual biomass, and its transportability.

EURO-CROP-Map classifications are primarily based on SAR data, which have the advantage of not being affected by cloud cover and allow for constant and continuous analysis throughout the year. SAR images also use algorithms based on backscattering and radar variation, but they can present confusions. This is for instance what happened for table grapes in the Italian pilot (Figure 6). Because this plantation is subjected for a period of the season to coverage, it has not been recognized by JRC map and it has been considered as urban soil.

However, this limit could be solved with a simple albedo algorithm applied to optical data to distinguish between a covered agricultural field and an urban area.

The main shortcomings of EURO-CROP-Map concern the classification of urban areas. For the sake of the project, it is crucial to clearly distinguish urban areas from non-urban ones. To this end, we have integrated OpenStreetMap (OSM) data to create a 10m buffer around roads and have used Open Buildings V3 Polygons data to exclude buildings from the mappings. Additionally, for bare soils and anthropic areas such as parking lots and concrete areas, we have used interferometric data with a 90m baseline (with two images over a 27-day period) from Sentinel-1 SLC images.

The difference between the urban classification of EURO-CROP-Map and the classification created for TEAPOTS is presented in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Furthermore, while EURO-CROP-Map offers good crop classification for each crop type, for the project purposes a distinction between temporary and permanent crops was enough. For temporary crops, we have considered seasonality and the growth cycle, using a moisture index, a thermal index, and have analysed the trend of the vegetative index. However, also when performing crop type classification, EURO-CROP-Map has

incurred in inaccuracies, identifying crops which are not present in the pilot units. The differences between the temporary crop map from TEAPOTS and EUROCROPMAP are visible in Figure 8 and Figure 9.

Regarding permanent crops, EUROCROPMAP considers a unique class named “300 Woodland and Shrubland”. This class includes forests and permanent crops, making it inadequate for biomass estimation. Therefore, we have trained a specific training set for the crops of each pilot unit and reclassified the images monthly, obtaining twelve annual matrices useful for classifying the different permanent crops. Figure 10 and Figure 11 shows the different results between TEAPOTS and EUROCROPMAP mapping, highlighting the improvements achieved with our customized approach. We have decided not to include the “500 Grassland” class (permanent and temporary) as a permanent crop because, although it is permanent, it does not produce a relevant "herbaceous" residue for our purposes, preferring to consider it as temporary crop.

In conclusion, the EUROCROPMAP will still be considered for future tests on virtual pilots, despite it is not sufficiently accurate for the project goal. Moreover, being a triennial map, it would not adequately support the constant monitoring of the physical and virtual pilot, as required within the project framework. Therefore, we have chosen to develop an *ad hoc* map for the project which has provided satisfactory results. Moreover, the mapping activities will continue all over the project to reduce remaining errors and make necessary corrections to improve the accuracy of results.

Classification maps developed for the project for both pilot sites can be consulted on the [project website](#).

3. Biomass maps

To estimate Above Ground Biomass (AGB) based on a land cover map and appropriate classification, a Random Forest regression has been employed. The methodology for biomass estimation has been reported below.

3.1 Biomass estimation methodology

Firstly, data have been pre-processed: Sentinel-2 images have been used to create an annual composite representing the pixel value averages. Sentinel-1 satellite radar images have been then applied to establish the vegetation structure of the areas and perform land cover analysis. Elevation data from SRTM 3sec DEM (Digital Elevation Model) and Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) Level 4A (L4A) Version 2 data have been integrated to represent terrain elevation and above-ground biomass density (AGBD) and its standard error estimates, respectively. Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellites have been chosen for their complementarity: Sentinel-1 provides backscatter coefficients at different polarizations, while Sentinel-2 offers high spectral resolution, including the Red-Edge (RE) spectral region, relevant for above-ground biomass estimation. AGB measures vegetation

biomass which is defined as “the total amount of plant-derived living and dead organic matter per unit of surface area”[4].

Sentinel-1 data processing is performed through radiometric calibration, noise reduction (speckle filtering), terrain radiometric levelling, and geometric correction. For Sentinel-2 data, a cloud-free image with 13 spectral bands is downloaded, then orthorectified and converted to surface reflectance.

The second step has required the construction of the regression model: images have been resampled onto a larger grid to improve spatial accuracy and reduce noise. Following the extraction of feature layers from the combination of Sentinel-2 bands, DEM, and GEDI through stratified sampling to include only unmasked pixels, the regression model has been trained.

Optical satellite and SAR data have been employed to estimate AGB. After that, vegetation indices and spectral reflectance have been computed as predictors for AGB estimation, based on red, RE, and near-infrared (NIR) bands. The Random Forest regression model has been trained to handle large datasets and capture non-linear relationships between variables.

This trained model has been applied to predict AGB values in different areas. Root mean square error (RMSE) and the correlation coefficient R^2 have been computed to evaluate the model performance in terms of prediction accuracy and reliability.

The scatter plot presented below (Figure 12) represents above-ground biomass density measured in megagrams per hectare (Mg/ha). The plots for both pilots show:

- X-axis (Observed): Displays observed values of biomass density.
- Y-axis (Predicted): Displays predicted values of biomass density.
- Data Points: Points are represented as grey triangles showing the relationship between observed and predicted values.
- Linear Regression Line: The line represents the linear fit of data, with a regression formula that includes R^2 (coefficient of determination).

FIGURE 12. R^2 COEFFICIENT FOR ITALIAN PILOT (UP) AND GREEK PILOT (DOWN)

The graph depicts how predicted values of biomass density compare with observed values. The R^2 value and the regression line show the model's performance in predicting biomass density values. For the Greek Pilot, R^2 value is 0.81 with RMSE=2.35 while for the Italian one R^2 value is 0.78 with RMSE=9.51 indicating that 81% and 78% of the variability in observed biomass density values can be explained by the values predicted by the model.

The graph and statistical analysis have revealed that predicted values of above-ground biomass correlate positively with observed values. This suggests that the linear regression model used is effective in predicting biomass density based on direct measurements.

Final map images of above-ground biomass (AGB) for both pilots are reported below. The maps of AGB for both pilots can be consulted on the [project website](#).

FIGURE 13. AGB (KG/M²) OF THE ITALIAN PILOT. PLOTS ARE DELIMITED BY BLACK BORDERS. THE IMAGE DISPLAYS THE AGB AVAILABLE RANGING FROM 0 KG (VINE SHOOTS) TO A MAXIMUM VALUE OF 69.90 KG

FIGURE 14. AGB (KG/M²) OF THE GREEK PILOT. PLOTS ARE DELIMITED BY BLACK BORDER. THE IMAGE DISPLAYS THE AGB AVAILABLE RANGING FROM 1.41 KG TO A MAXIMUM VALUE OF 5.08 KG.

Figure 13 and Figure 14 demonstrate that the pilot extension has a larger impact on the availability of total biomass, resulting in higher values of AGB in Italy compared to those in Greece.

4. Residual biomass and potential exploitation maps

The last map identifies locations where residual biomass is generated and provides suggestion on the best ways to exploit it. The methodology for measuring the annual quantity of residual biomass or residues produced by crops and the information on the potential fuel for energy production is described below.

FIGURE 15. RESIDUAL BIOMASS (KG/M²) OF THE ITALIAN PILOT. THE IMAGE DISPLAYS THE RESIDUAL BIOMASS AVAILABLE RANGING FROM 21.37 KG TO A MAXIMUM VALUE OF 41.59 KG

FIGURE 16. RESIDUAL BIOMASS (KG/M²) OF THE GREEK PILOT. THE IMAGE DISPLAYS THE RESIDUAL BIOMASS AVAILABLE RANGING FROM 1.60 KG TO A MAXIMUM VALUE OF 2.71 KG

Consequently, Figure 15 and Figure 16 demonstrate that the pilot extension has also a larger impact on the availability of residual biomass, resulting in higher values of residual biomass in Italy compared to those in Greece.

4.1 Residual biomass estimation methodology

The first phase consists of identifying and defining the study areas where residual biomasses will be generated. A surface layer is created by excluding parts of the terrain unsuitable for biomass production, such as roads, buildings, and bodies of water.

The DEM layer has been then integrated to exclude areas with slope greater than 25%. This serves to avoid including areas unsuitable for residue collection, reducing the risk of erosion and soil damage. Moreover, areas with high slopes that make transportation and harvesting difficult are also excluded.

A road accessibility layer has been developed: areas too distant from main roads or with narrow access roads are excluded. Additionally, the speed of travel on roads is considered to classify and assess area accessibility.

The crop classification process described in paragraph **2.1. Classification methodology** and the estimation biomass methodology presented in paragraph **3.1. Biomass estimation methodology** have been also integrated into the model to add the crop classification map and the biomass map in the workflow.

The fifth layer is represented by time: it evaluates the temporal availability of residues and the time required for their transport, which is crucial for effective planning of residue harvest and transport.

The last step consists of overlapping all layers to estimate the quantity of residual biomass produced by selected crops. This provides a quantitative assessment of available biomass per year, expressed as ton year⁻¹, to clearly measure the available resource for energy production.

The workflow of the applied methodology is presented in the image below: processes are represented by squares, while outputs are depicted as ellipses.

FIGURE 17. WORKFLOW OF RESIDUAL BIOMASS ESTIMATION

Residual biomass and potential exploitation maps can be consulted on the [project website](#). The maps allow to understand, for each crop type, its transportability (in %). As soon as the TDP will be developed, these maps will be transformed into interactive isochrone maps.

4.2 Data validation

To validate residual biomass in physical pilots two different approaches have been considered.

For the Italian pilot, considering the drought condition that the pilot has experienced during the current season as further explained in paragraph 6. **Encountered issues and mitigation actions**, it has been agreed to validate satellite data for residual biomass with the available pruning (peach trees) and historical data/scientific literature (other plants) registered by Ecofarm.

TABLE 4. PRUNING FOR THE ITALIAN PILOT

Plantation type	Pruning (Kg/plant)
Vineyards	Between 2-3
Table grape	4
Peach and Apricot Trees	Between 6 and 8

Data refers to adult plants (usually after 3 and 4 years-old for vineyards, grape trees, peach and apricot trees). When a unique value was not available, the mean value has been considered.

For the Greek pilot, instead, the pruning protocol has been provided by CERTH for vineyard while for almond trees [5] and orchards [6], data from literature have been retrieved.

TABLE 5. PRUNING FOR THE GREEK PILOT

Plantation type	Pruning (Kg/plant)
Vineyards	Between 0.8 – 1.2

Validation results for both pilots are reported below.

Regarding virtual pilots, as also temporary crops will be considered, the harvest method and relative harvest indexes will be employed. Harvest Index (HI) refers to “the ratio between the dry yield (including red, green, and rotten production) and dry above ground biomass”. This value, expressed as percentage, is usually retrieved from literature for each crop species under non-stress conditions [7].

HI to be employed during the project has been provided by UNIPD-TESAF and reported below.

TABLE 6. HARVEST INDEXES FOR TEMPORARY CROPS

Crop type and use ⁵	Production (t/ha) ⁶	Production expressed as dry matter (t/ha)	Sustainable removal rates (%) ^[8]	Harvest index (%)	Dry matter (%)
Maize - Grain	10.9	9.446		52% ^[7]	87%
Maize – Biomass only	-	8.719	50%	-	-
Durum wheat – Grain	5.8	4.910		48% ^[9]	85%
Durum wheat – Biomass only	-	5.319	40%	-	-
Ensiled durum wheat – Biomass and grain	37.8	15.120	-	100%	40%
Rapeseed - Grain	3.3	2.466	-	30% ^[9]	74%
Rapeseed – Biomass only	-	5.755	50%	-	-
Sunflower - Grain	3.5	3.261		27% ^[10]	93%
Sunflower – Biomass only	-	8.816	50%	-	-
Silage ryegrass – Biomass and grain	24.9	11.200	-	100%	45%
Silage triticale – Biomass and grain	39.5	11.850	-	100%	30%
Beetroot - Root	65.6	17.706	-	85% ^[11]	27%
Beetroot – Biomass only	-	3.125	50%	-	-
Oat – Grain	3.9	3.132	-	52% ^[10]	80%
Oat – Biomass only	-	2.891	40%	-	-
Soft wheat - Grain	6.6	5.637		48% ^[9]	85%
Soft wheat – Biomass only	-	6.107	40%	-	-
Ensiled soft wheat – Biomass and grain	37.8	15.120	-	100%	40%
Barley - Grain	6.2	4.083	-	53% ^[9]	66%
Barley - Biomass only	-	3.621	40%	-	-

⁵ Two harvesting techniques can be employed: a whole crop harvesting where the entire plant is chopped at the waxy stage. In this case, the resulting biomass is used entirely. For selective grain harvesting, instead, only the grain is harvested, while the rest of the plant (biomass) is left in the field. This detail is specified in the table. Therefore, missing values can be either Non Applicable or Not Available.

⁶ Average value from the Venetian Authority for Agricultural Payment (AVEPA) and Italian National Institute for Statistics (ISTAT) for Veneto Region.

Ensiled barley -Biomass and grain	37.8	9.752		100%	26%
Sorghum - Grain	70.9	61.714		52%[7]	87%
Sorghum - Biomass only		56.967	50%		

For future releases, also data from IoTs will be included for validation purposes.

5. Results

In this chapter, we will report the results obtained from this study by detailing both pilots and sharing initial impressions. It is important to point out that maps will undergo further integration, and the collected data will be subjected to additional analysis and in-depth examination.

AGB data have been converted from Mg/ha^{-1} , which is the standard unit of measurement for this type of data, to Kg/ha^{-1} to allow for clearer interpretation and better standardization of results in the table.

TABLE 7. VALIDATION RESULTS FOR THE ITALIAN PILOT

Plot number	Crop type	Pruning per plot (Kg)	Pruning per plant (Kg) ⁷	Residual biomass per plot (Kg) ⁸	Age	Plants number	Mean AGB per plot
ECOFARM 0	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	5600	2	5591.743	1	2800	25.77
ECOFARM 1	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	32622	6	30803.26	3	5437	27.32
ECOFARM 2	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	20657	7	18522.08	5	2951	28.83
ECOFARM 3	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	14427	7	12702.62	5	2061	29.35

⁷ Pruning per plant are average values retrieved from Table 4.

⁸ Value retrieved from AGB and validated through pruning per plant and pruning per plot data.

Plot number	Crop type	Pruning per plot (Kg)	Pruning per plant (Kg) ⁷	Residual biomass per plot (Kg) ⁸	Age	Plants number	Mean AGB per plot
ECOFARM 4	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	12040	7	11147.55	5	1720	27.87
ECOFARM 5	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	6097	7	5592.742	5	871	28.17
ECOFARM 6	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	9170	7	8525.171	5	1310	27.72
ECOFARM 7	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	11232	8	10691.12	7	1404	27.07
ECOFARM 8	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	-	-	-	0	850	25.42
ECOFARM 9	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	4445	7	4255.333	22	635	26.92
ECOFARM 10	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	870	2	871.48	1	435	25.70
ECOFARM 11	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	27400	5	26675.78	18	5480	26.52
ECOFARM 12	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	26240	4	26073.74	5	6560	26.00
ECOFARM 13	Temporary crops	-	-	-	0	-	27.10
ECOFARM 14	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	13880	4	-	13	3470	27.50

Plot number	Crop type	Pruning per plot (Kg)	Pruning per plant (Kg) ⁷	Residual biomass per plot (Kg) ⁸	Age	Plants number	Mean AGB per plot
ECOFARM 15	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	120000	3	119930.5	2	40000	25.77
ECOFARM 16	Temporary crops	-	-	-	0	-	25.94
ECOFARM 17	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	13912	4	-	12	3478	32.81
ECOFARM 18	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	9457	7	8794.915	17	1351	27.82
ECOFARM 19	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	8320	5	-	15	1664	28.76
ECOFARM 20	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	8960	5	8122.293	15	1792	28.57
ECOFARM 21	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	27520	4	26362.41	6	6880	26.89
ECOFARM 22	Fallow land - Temporary Crop	-	-	-	0	-	27.62
ECOFARM 23	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	9600	4	8745.522	12	2400	28.30
ECOFARM 24	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	15804	4	-	13	3951	30.43
ECOFARM 25	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	21760	4	20552.11	6	5440	27.29
ECOFARM 26	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	48000	4	45299.7	12	12000	27.29

Plot number	Crop type	Pruning per plot (Kg)	Pruning per plant (Kg) ⁷	Residual biomass per plot (Kg) ⁸	Age	Plants number	Mean AGB per plot
ECOFARM 27	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	150000	5	147690.9	7	30000	26.15
ECOFARM 28	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	24122	7	22102.85	21	3446	28.24
ECOFARM 29	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	48000	4	46475.97	12	12000	26.71
ECOFARM 30	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	38843	7	34938.65	11	5549	28.80
ECOFARM 31	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	2303	7	2197.571	7	329	27.10
ECOFARM 32	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	85000	5	79013.75	15	17000	27.75
ECOFARM 33	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	10000	5	9273.929	15	2000	27.77
ECOFARM 34	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	-	-	-	-	-	27.70
ECOFARM 35	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	7740	5	7604.611	15	1548	26.18
ECOFARM 36	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	9600	2	9552.514	1	4800	25.86
ECOFARM 37	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	32000	5	-	14	6400	31.08
ECOFARM 38	Peach trees -	-	-	-	-	-	27.54

Plot number	Crop type	Pruning per plot (Kg)	Pruning per plant (Kg) ⁷	Residual biomass per plot (Kg) ⁸	Age	Plants number	Mean AGB per plot
	Permanent Crop						
ECOFARM 39	Vineyard - Permanent Crop	32800	5	32817.52	8	6560	25.73
ECOFARM 40	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	8225	7	7740.299	16	1175	27.44
ECOFARM 41	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	6398	7	6377	7	914	25.83
ECOFARM 42	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	40201	7	35251.07	11	5743	29.61
ECOFARM 43	Peach trees - Permanent Crop	29358	7	26845.88	14	4194	28.24
ECOFARM 44	Vine shoot - Permanent Crop	-	-	0	-	8000	25.54

Based on some observations, the average above-ground biomass per plot varies from 25.42 Kg (ECOFARM 8) to 32.81 Kg (ECOFARM 17). This variability can be attributed to several factors such as crop type, plant age, management practices and plant density.

The effect of crop type can be summarised as follows:

- **Peach orchards:** They have an average AGB ranging from 25.42 Kg to 29.61 Kg, with most plots between 27 Kg and 29 Kg.
- **Vineyards:** They show a slightly wider range of AGB, from 25.54 Kg to 32.81 Kg, indicating greater variability in management and growing conditions.

Among the results of this study, it appears that older plants tend to have higher AGB. For example, ECOFARM 17, with 12-year-old plants, has an AGB of 32.81 Kg. Younger plants (1-5 years) show a generally lower AGB, indicating a positive correlation between plant age and accumulated biomass.

Plant density also affects AGB. For example, in plots with a larger number of plants, the AGB tends to be higher. ECOFARM 15, with 40000 plants, has an AGB of 25.77 Kg, while ECOFARM 17, with 3478 plants, has an AGB of 32.81 Kg. This might indicate that although plant density increases the total biomass, the AGB per plant might decrease. This is likely because a higher number of plants competing for the same limited resources can restrict the growth of individual plants. However, we cannot exclude possible correlations between planting layout, space, canopy height and soil type (bare/ inbred).

Regarding plot-specific observations we can report:

- ECOFARM 0: Peach orchards with AGB of 25.77 Kg, represents one of the lowest values for peach orchards, potentially due to the young age of the plants (1 year).
 - ECOFARM 27: Vineyard with very high pruning and biomass, and an AGB of 26.15 Kg, suggesting intensive management practices.
 - ECOFARM 17: Vineyard with the highest AGB value (32.81 Kg), which could be the result of a combination of plant age (12 years) and optimal management.
 - ECOFARM 42: Peach orchards with one of the highest AGB values (29.61 kg), which could be due to a combination of plant age and pruning techniques.
- ECOFARM 14-19-37-24-17: They do not have the Residual biomass values per plot because they are covered by a protective tarpaulin which, although showing an AGB (Errata) value, is masked by the classification performed during the cover crop.
- ECOFARM 44: has a value of 0, because the crop is less than one year old since planting.

These observations highlight the variability and dynamics present in the different plots, indicating that factors such as plant age, density and management practices play a crucial role in determining AGB.

TABLE 8. VALIDATION RESULTS FOR THE GREEK PILOT

Plot number	Crop type	Pruning per plot (Kg) ⁹	Pruning per plant (Kg)	Residual biomass per plot (Kg) ¹⁰	Age	Plants number	Mean AGB per plot
FILIA GHI A1	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	3600	0.8	1420.99	4	4500	1.90

⁹ Only for plots A4 and A16 pruning protocols have been provided. For the other vineyards the value has been retrieved from values of pruning protocols.

¹⁰ Value retrieved from AGB and validated through pruning per plot data.

Plot number	Crop type	Pruning per plot (Kg) ⁹	Pruning per plant (Kg)	Residual biomass per plot (Kg) ¹⁰	Age	Plants number	Mean AGB per plot
FILIA GHI A2	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	2200	0.8	2153.69	20	2750	2.08
FILIA GHI A3	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	1320	0.8	1318.26	4	1650	1.73
FILIA GHI A4	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	1500 ¹¹	1	1475.00	16	1500	1.78
FILIA GHI A5	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	288	0.9	282.45	4	320	1.77
FILIA GHI A6	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	-	-	-	4	650	-
FILIA GHI A7	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	450	0.9	427.41	14	500	1.87
FILIA GHI A8	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	1760	0.8	1733.09	4	2200	1.78
FILIA GHI A9	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	800	0.8	792.40	14	1000	1.91
FILIA GHI A10	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	1536	0.8	1456.50	16	1920	1.88
FILIA GHI A11	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	1350	0.9	1315.17	20	1500	1.85
FILIA GHI A12	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	900	0.9	888.18	18	1000	2.00
FILIA GHI A13	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	500	0.8	489.46	14	625	2.04
FILIA GHI A14	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	500	0.8	498.08	15	625	1.91
FILIA GHI A15	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	-	-	-	15	2000	-
FILIA GHI A16	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	1200 ¹²	0.8	1141.55	30	1500	2.01
FILIA GHI A17	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	880	0.8	846.88	-	1100	2.08
FILIA GHI A18	Vineyard – Permanent Crop	5200	0.8	5080.86	18	6500	2.19
FILIA GHI A19	Almond Trees – Permanent Crop	50.94[5]	-	50.862	4	-	1.77

¹¹ From pruning protocol provided by CERTH.

¹² From pruning protocol provided by CERTH.

Plot number	Crop type	Pruning per plot (Kg) ⁹	Pruning per plant (Kg)	Residual biomass per plot (Kg) ¹⁰	Age	Plants number	Mean AGB per plot
FILIA GHI A20	Almond Trees – Permanent Crop	83.54[5]	-	64.87	4	-	1.87
FILIA GHI A21	Almond Trees – Permanent Crop	52.07[5]	-	47.61	4	-	2.22
FILIA GHI A22	Almond Trees – Permanent Crop	36.22[5]	-	34.38	4	-	1.83
FILIA GHI A23	Olive Trees – Permanent Crop	86.94[6]	0.4	55.55	10	210	2.09

The data collected for the FILIA GHI plots show a variety of above ground biomass (AGB) values influenced by various factors such as crop type, pruning practices, plant age, and number of plants per plot.

These plots exhibit significantly lower AGB values compared to those observed in Sicily. Generally, plots like FILIA GHI A16 and FILIA GHI A18 consist of older plants (30 and 18 years respectively) compared to the Italian pilot, showing AGB values (2.01 Kg and 2.19 Kg) that also reflect the trend observed in the Italian pilot, where older plants have higher AGB compared to younger one from the same pilot. In FILIA GHI A3, in fact, which is 4-year-old plants, there is a lower AGB value (1.73 Kg), confirming lower biomass in younger plants.

Plant density also plays a role in AGB. For example, FILIA GHI A17, with 1100 plants, shows an AGB of 2.08 Kg, indicating a higher number of plants competing for the same limited resources and leaf mass compared to other vineyards.

Despite preliminary pruning data estimates, we are currently unable to describe and analyze specific anomalies due to the limited number of pruning. It is important to note, however, that the model shows satellite-derived residual biomass values similar to or close to the estimated values of collection, except in the case of FILIA GHI A1, for which we do not yet have a clear explanation. In any case, we have ensured that the data analyzed and collected during pre-analysis did not include cloud cover, external influences, or other factors that could have affected AGB.

Regarding transportability, it has been retrieved considering several input data such as roads' width, roads' speed limits and slopes. Once combined with residual biomass, the percentage and the value (Kg) of residual biomass transportability has been calculated for both pilots.

In general, as temporary crops present lower values of residual biomass compared to permanent crops this also impacts on the biomass transportability.

Regarding the Italian pilot, the graph below (Figure 18) illustrates the transportability for both temporary and permanent crops. Regarding temporary crops, the 5% of available residual biomass presents a transportability at 40%, 62% of available residual biomass presents a transportability at 60%, 21% of available residual biomass presents a transportability at 75% and only 12% of available residual biomass is fully transportable (100% of transportability).

Regarding permanent crops, instead, 8% of available residual biomass presents a transportability at 60%, while the remaining residual biomass presents a transportability rate at 75% (77% of residual biomass) and at 100% (15% of available biomass).

In conclusion, in the Italian pilot, despite the area orography, both temporary and permanent crops present a valuable percentage of transportability with permanent crops showing a transportability rate over 60%.

FIGURE 18. TRANSPORTABILITY OF RESIDUAL BIOMASS PER CROP TYPES IN THE ITALIAN PILOT

As far as the Greek pilot (Figure 19), considering the slope of the Greek pilot (almost a flat area), the whole residual biomass can be fully transported (transportability rate at 100%). However, it is important to note that temporary crops available in the Greek pilot do not produce significant residual biomass compared to the Italian pilot and, therefore, their value is equal to zero.

Moreover, only very limited areas, which are not part of the farm site but of the whole study area present a transportability rate at 60%, yet they refer to temporary crops where residual biomass is again equal to zero.

FIGURE 19. TRANSPORTABILITY OF RESIDUAL BIOMASS PER CROP TYPES IN THE GREEK PILOT

In conclusion, in the Greek pilot the whole residual biomass produced especially from permanent crops can be totally transported due to the orography of the territory. Regarding temporary crops, is important to remember that are not part of the TEAPOTS scope yet serve only as reference for the virtual pilot, as explained in paragraph 6. *Encountered issues and mitigation actions*. Therefore, despite their total transportability rate (100%), because of the type of temporary crop, no residual biomass is estimated to be available.

6. Encountered issues and mitigation actions

During the project implementation, several unexpected challenges have arisen related to the pilot specifications. We have addressed these issues through discussions with partners, the WP leader, and the project coordinator. Below is a detailed breakdown of the challenges and corresponding mitigation actions.

Challenge 1: Difficulty mapping arboreal crops with satellites

Problem: Dense canopy cover of arboreal crops, particularly vineyards with specific row layouts and inclinations, hinders detection by optical and SAR sensors, even at good resolutions. Additionally, especially in southern Europe, vineyards are subjected to grape covering practices for an approximate period of three months, depending on farmer's requirements. This practice protects the plant from climatic agents such as hailstorms[12]. Simultaneously, it masks crops for satellite sensors passage.

Mitigation actions:

1. Satellites limits in capturing arboreal crops are usually mitigated by data fusion techniques. This approach is characterized by the combination or “fusion” of images derived from different sensors, creating a composite image with high spectral and spatial resolution[13]. Therefore, data fusion technique has been employed to better capture arboreal crops.
2. Regarding grape coverage, this practice has been implemented only in the Italian pilot, while it has not been adopted in the Greek one. For this case, it has been decided to use satellite images for the uncovered period and statistical estimation of biomass retrieved from literature for the covered period to ensure these crops can also be accounted for waste production.

Challenge 2: Limited biomes representativeness for virtual pilots

Problem: Both the Italian and the Greek pilot (physical pilots) are in southern Europe and are characterized not only by similar cultivations (mainly arboreal and vineyards) but also by similar climatic conditions. However, they differ significantly from the virtual pilots, which are instead located in northern Europe. This results in different crops, with a prevalence of herbaceous crops in the north, and in different climatic conditions, with higher northern countries’ exposition to cloudiness. This limits optical sensors to monitor the interested areas, resulting in a reduced number of visible images over the year compared to those retrieved from southern countries.

Mitigation actions:

1. To enhance the representativeness of physical pilots, it has been agreed to study herbaceous crops from the surroundings of the physical pilots to evaluate theoretical biomass availability.
2. For cloudiness, this will be addressed through data fusion techniques, combining optical images with SAR ones, which instead are not sensitive to clouds.

Challenge 3: Lack of available agricultural waste in the Italian pilot and limited ground truth values for both pilots.

Problem: Since the beginning of the project, Sicily region, where the Italian pilot is located, has been affected by a severe drought, with negative impacts on agricultural irrigation and production (European Union, 2024). This has resulted in very little production of pruning in the Italian pilot, which, however, is crucial for satellite data validation.

In general, in both pilots ground truth values for satellite data validation are limited to some plots/plantation type.

Mitigation actions:

1. Available pruning waste from the current season and historical averages or scientific literature data has been accounted in the Italian pilot, to compensate for drought limitations.

2. It is expected to increase the number of ground truth data during the project lifetime to improve the validation performance.

Challenge 4: Substitution of the Greek pilot

Problem: The initially identified Greek pilot withdrew from the project. Despite the tempestive intervention of the project coordinator and local partners to identify a new partner with similar characteristics, this has inevitably caused a delay in data and map collection.

Mitigation actions:

1. We have prioritized the Italian pilot to develop the methodology and address other challenges. This initial focus proved advantageous when the new Greek pilot came onboard. Furthermore, we have ensured indirect communication with the new Greek pilot, before their official accession approval, thanks to the support of the CERTH to smooth mapping activities.
2. In agreement with and with the support of the WP leader and the project coordinator, we have requested a deliverable submission extension to ensure quality and timely results.

7. Conclusion

Three annual maps have been created for the two physical pilots located respectively in Italy and Greece. One map presents the total available biomass in the pilot sites. Another map shows the residual biomass available in the pilot sites which can be used as agricultural waste for renewable energy production and plant biostimulant products development. The last map allows users to better exploit available residual maps to develop by-products (renewable energy and plant biostimulants) and locate *in-situ* plants. All maps are available on the [project website](#) and will be updated yearly. Furthermore, the same methodology will be replicated for virtual pilots.

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